

***o*-Aminophenylhydrazine and some Interesting Heterocyclic Compounds Derived from it. Part IV.**

Lengthened *o*-Diderivatives of Benzene and their Ring-closure.

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In Part III (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 561) the reaction of *o*-aminophenyl-4R-thiosemicarbazides with thiocarbimides, carbimides, potassium cyanate and thiocyanate, aldehydes etc. and the behaviour of the compounds thus obtained towards different types of ring-closing agents have been described. In this part the action of isocyanates, isothiocyanates, aldehydes, ferric chloride and hydrazine hydrate, etc. upon aminophenylsemicarbazides as also the ring closure of some of the lengthened *o*-diderivatives of benzene by the action of hydrochloric acid, etc., and also the ring-closure of some typical derivatives of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine on reduction will be described.

o-Nitrophenylhydrazine reacts with phenyl cyanate to yield *o*-nitrophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide (I) which in its turn gives two products on reduction, one being 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide (II) and the other 1-phenyl-2:3-benzo-6-keto-1:4:5-triazine (III).

Evidently, the triazine (III) is formed from 1-aminophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide (II) by the loss of one molecule of ammonia in presence of strong hydrochloric acid. This view gets additional

support from the fact that the amino compound on treatment with acetic anhydride or with strong hydrochloric acid has been found to yield the same benzo-triazine compound.

1-*o*-Aminophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide readily reacts with potassium cyanate, phenylisocyanate, phenyl mustard oil and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde to yield respectively 1-carbamido-2-phenyl semicarbazido-benzene (IV), 1-phenylcarbamido 2-phenylsemicarbazido-benzene (V), 1-phenyl-thiocarbamido-2-phenylsemicarbazido-benzene (VI) and 1-nitrobenzalanilido-2-phenylsemicarbazido-benzene (VII):

The first of the above four compounds loses a molecule of water on being treated with strong hydrochloric acid yielding 2:3-benzo-6-phenylamino-8-keto-1:4:5:7 octatetrazine (VIII).

and is identical with the compound obtained from 1-carbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbazido-benzene by the action of the same reagent (Part III, page 570).

Ferric chloride exerts its oxidising action upon 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide similarly as in the case of the corresponding thio compounds, to yield 3:4-benzo-7-phenylamino-1:2:5:6-oxheptatriazine (IX), thus:

Stolle (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1903, **68**, 137; 1904, **70**, 395, 414) similarly obtained oxiazole derivatives by oxidising acylhydrazones of aldehydes.

Hydrazine hydrate reacts with 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide exactly in the same manner as has been observed with the corresponding thio compound (Part III. page 571) to yield 1-*N*-phenyl-3:4-benzo-7-hydroxy-1:2:5:6-heptatetrazine (X), thus:

Formation of hetero-cyclic compounds from suitable *ortho*-nitro derivatives of benzene by reduction is well known. Paal (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 959, 3059) and Busch (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2899) prepared *N*-phenyliminazoles by reducing *o*-nitro-benzylanilines and Hobrecker (*Ber.*, 1872, 5, 920) prepared benziminazole by reducing *o*-nitroacetanilide. Guha and De prepared a large number of poly-hetero-atomic compounds by reducing *o*-nitro-(also hydroxy)-benzaldehyde-*o*-nitrophenylhydrazones, *o*-nitrophenylhydrazones of 1:2-diketones and *o*:*o*'-nitro-amino-diphenyl-hydrazine (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 41). *o*-Nitro-phenylhydrazine has now been made to react with potassium cyanate, potassium thiocyanate, *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, glyoxal, carbondisulphide and methyl iodide in presence of potassium hydroxide, carbonyl chloride, ethyl chloroformate, etc., to yield 1-*o*-nitrophenyl-semicarbazide (XI), 1-*o*-nitrophenyl-thiosemicarbazide (XII), *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde-*o*-nitrophenylhydrazone (XIII), glyoxal-*o*-nitrophenylosazone (XIV), *o*-nitrophenyl-methyl-dithiocarbazine (XV), di-*o*-nitrophenyl-carbohydrazide (XVI) and ethyl-*o*-nitrophenylcarbazine (XVII) respectively, thus:—

Both the compounds (XI) and (XII) on reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid give the same benzo-triazine derivative (XVIII), by losing one molecule of water and sulphuretted hydrogen respectively from the intermediate aminophenyl-semicarbazide and aminophenyl-thiosemicarbazide, thus:—

It is noteworthy that the intermediate amino-compounds formed in the first stage of the reduction processes cannot be isolated; (compare the simultaneous formation and isolation of the amino-compounds II, IV, VIII of Part III). This shows that the *o*-aminophenyl-semicarbazide and *o*-aminophenyl-thiosemicarbazide possess a greater tendency to form ring-closed compounds in presence of hydrochloric acid than compounds in which the CONH_2 and CSNH_2 groups are substituted. Another point of considerable significance is that the end carbonamide (CONH_2) and thiocarbonamide (CSNH_2)

groupings being unsubstituted, the nature of ring-closure differs remarkably from that observed in the formation of compound III (also of III and VI of Part III) where the carbonamide groupings are substituted: in the former case the ring closure is effected with the elimination of water or sulphuretted hydrogen and in the latter with the elimination of ammonia.

o-Chlorobenzaldehyde-nitrophenylhydrazone (XIII) on reduction furnishes the unstable amino-compound from which 2:3:7:8-dibenzo-1:4:5-octatriazine (XIX) is formed by the loss of one molecule of hydrochloric acid, thus:

Glyoxal-nitrophenylosazone (XIV) on reduction gives similarly as the mono μ -benziminazole formation of Guha and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 86) the bis-benziminazole compound (XX), thus:

Bis-benziminazole was prepared by Hubner (*Annalen*, 1881, 209, 339) by reducing *o*-nitro-oxanilides.

o-Nitrophenyl-methyl-dithiocarbazine (XV) on reduction forms the unstable amino compound which loses a molecule of sulphuretted hydrogen to yield methylthiol-benzotriazine (XXI), thus:

Arndt and Rosenau (*Ber.*, 1917, **50**, 1248) prepared μ -phenotriazoxine-mercaptan by the action of alkali upon *o*-nitrophenylthiourea and by reducing it with zinc dust and alkali obtained β -phenotriazine mercaptan of the formula,

Di-*o*-nitrophenyl carbonylhydrazide (XVI) on reduction yields di-benzo-deca-pentazine (XXII), thus:

For similar poly-hetero-ring formations, compare Thiele and Holzinger (*Annalen*, 1899, **305**, 100) and Duval (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1910, **7**, 730) who prepared imino-dibenzyl by heating 2:2'-diamino-dibenzyl and azo-diphenylethane by reducing 2:2'-dinitro-diphenylethane with zinc dust in presence of aqueous alcoholic baryta.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Nitrophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide (I).—Phenylisocyanate (3.5 g.) was added slowly under shaking to an aqueous solution of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride (5 g.). The reaction took place at once with the evolution of heat and frothing and the separation of a yellow precipitate which was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in beautiful yellow plates, m.p. 202°. It is soluble in acetone, pyridine, acetic acid, sparingly soluble in cold water but readily soluble in hot water. (Found: N, 20.47. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$ requires N, 20.58 per cent.)

Reduction of o-Nitrophenyl-semicarbazide: Formation of 1-o-Amino-phenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide (II) and 1-Phenyl-2:3-benzo-6-keto-1:4:5-triazine (III).—The semicarbazide (5 g.) was heated with granulated tin (15 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) on a water-bath under reflux for 2-3 hours when a clear yellow solution was obtained. The solution was further heated on a

water-bath for about an hour more when the solution became quite colourless. The solution after cooling was diluted with about 150 c.c. water when a white solid (i) separated out, the filtered solution (ii) was kept for further treatment.

Isolation of Compound (III).—The white solid (i) was crystallised from dilute alcohol in beautiful white prisms, m.p. 170-171°. It is soluble in hot water and in cold dilute alkali (yield, 0.7 gm.). (Found: N, 18.52. $C_{13}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 18.66 per cent.).

Isolation of Compound (II).—The clear filtrate (ii) was largely diluted with water and tin was removed by passing sulphuretted hydrogen and the filtered solution was evaporated almost to dryness on the water-bath when reddish brown crystals were obtained. The compound was further purified by adding ether to an alcoholic solution of the substance and the white shining crystalline mass thus obtained was finally recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 250-251° with decomposition producing a blue colouration after darkening at 210°. It changes to reddish brown on standing. It is highly soluble in water and gives a red azo-dye on diazotisation and coupling with β -naphthol. (Found: N, 20.39. $C_{13}H_{14}ON_4 \cdot HCl$ requires N, 20.14 per cent.).

The free Base.—One gram of the above hydrochloride was dissolved in the least quantity of water and ammonia added drop by drop until just alkaline. A brownish precipitate separated out which was, after filtration and washing with water, crystallised from alcohol in brownish needles, m.p. 145°. (Found: N, 23.27. $C_{13}H_{14}ON_4$ requires N, 23.14 per cent.).

Action of Acetic Anhydride upon 1-o-Aminophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide.—The semicarbazide hydrochloride (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) on a sand-bath under reflux for about 20 minutes and the clear solution was poured into water when a brownish white crystalline mass separated out. A second crop was obtained by concentrating the solution. On crystallisation from dilute alcohol it yielded white shining prisms, m.p. 170-171° (yield, 0.4 gm.). (Found: N, 18.59. $C_{13}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 18.66 per cent.). The compound is evidently identical with compound (III) which was also proved by taking the mixed melting point.

1-Phenylcarbamido-2-phenylsemicarbazido-benzene (V).—Phenyl isocyanate (0.5 g.) was added drop by drop to 1-o-aminophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride (1 g.) dissolved in the smallest

quantity of water under constant stirring when a brownish white precipitate separated out. It was crystallised from alcohol in white shining rectangular plates, m.p. above 290°. (Found: N, 19.45. $C_{20}H_{19}O_2N_8$ requires N, 19.39 per cent.).

1-Carbamido-2-phenylsemicarbazido-benzene (IV).—Potassium cyanate (0.6 g.) dissolved in the smallest quantity of water was added drop by drop under cooling to 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride (2 g.) also dissolved in the smallest quantity of water. A white solid came out at once which was filtered, washed with water and was finally crystallised from dilute alcohol as white plates which did not melt even at 290°. It is soluble in hot water and in cold alkali. (Found: N, 24.52. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2N_8$ requires N, 24.56 per cent.).

Action of strong Hydrochloric Acid upon Compound (IV) : Formation of 2:3-Benzo-6-phenylamino-8-keto-1:4:5:7-octatetrazine (VIII).—Two gm. of the above compound (IV) was heated with 100 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19) for about an hour and the clear solution thus obtained was poured into water when a shining white crystalline mass was obtained. A second crop was obtained by evaporating the mother-liquor. It was finally crystallised from dilute alcohol in white plates, m.p. 145-146° (yield, 1.2 gm.). (Found: N, 26.06. $C_{14}H_{15}ON_8$ requires N, 26.22 per cent.). The identity of this substance with compound XVII of Part III was proved by taking a mixed melting point.

1-Phenylthiocarbamido-2-phenylsemicarbazido-benzene (VI).—An alcoholic solution of 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylsemicarbazide (1 g.) and phenyl mustard oil (0.5 g.) was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 2-3 hours. The reaction product was then poured into water when a brownish white mass separated out which was crystallised from dilute alcohol as brownish white plates, m.p. above 290°. It is soluble in hot water and in cold concentrated alkali (yield, 1.2 gm.) (Found: N, 18.63. $C_{20}H_{19}ON_8S$ requires N, 18.57 per cent.).

*1-*o*-Nitrobenzalunilido-2-phenylsemicarbazido-benzene* (VII).—An alcoholic solution of 1-*o*-aminophenyl-2-phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride (1 g.) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.5 g.) was heated under reflux for about an hour. The clear solution on cooling gave a crystalline product which after filtration under pump and washing with a small quantity of cold alcohol was crystallised from alcohol.

m. p. 245-246° (yield, 0.6 gm.). (Found: N, 18.24. $C_{10}H_8O_2N_4$ requires N, 18.67 per cent.)

Action of Ferric Chloride upon (II): Formation of 3:4-Benzo-7-phenylamino-1:2:5:6-oxheptatriazine (IX).—The method of preparation was the same as that of the compound (XVIII) of Part III. The hydrochloride was crystallised from water slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid in beautiful reddish brown needles which did not melt even at 290°. (Found: N, 20.12. $C_{11}H_8ON_4.HCl$ requires N, 20.29 per cent.)

Action of Hydrazine Hydrate upon 1-o-Aminophenyl-4-phenyl semicarbazide: Formation of 1-N-Phenyl-3:4-benzo-7-hydroxy-1:4:5:6-heptatetrazine (X).—An alcoholic solution of 1-o-aminophenyl-4-phenyl semicarbazide (2 g.) and hydrazine hydrate (0.4 g.) were heated under reflux for about forty minutes. The solution on cooling gave a brownish white crystalline mass which was filtered, washed successively with alcohol and water and crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless shining needles, m. p. 90-91°. It is soluble in hot water and cold dilute alkali. (Found: N, 23.02. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_4$ requires N, 23.33 per cent.)

o-Nitrophenyl semicarbazide (XI).—An aqueous solution of potassium cyanate (1 g.) was drop by drop added under cooling to a very concentrated solution of o-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride (2 g.). The reaction took place instantaneously and a yellow solid was soon precipitated which was purified by dissolving in the minimum quantity of hot alcohol and scratching the sides of the containing vessel when cold. The fine yellow crystalline powder melted at 225° with decomposition. It is sparingly soluble in hot water but readily soluble in acetic acid and pyridine. (Found: N, 28.49. $C_7H_6O_3N_4$ requires N, 28.57 per cent.)

Reduction of Compound (XI): Formation of 2:3-Benzo-5-imino-1:4:6-triazine (XVIII).—o-Nitrophenyl semicarbazide (5 g.) was heated with granulated tin (10 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 c. c.) in a flask fitted with an upright condenser. After an hour, a light yellow clear solution was obtained which, however, became colourless on further heating. The solution was then largely diluted with water and tin removed by sulphuretted hydrogen. The solution was then evaporated almost to dryness on the water-bath and the reddish-brown crystalline residue thus obtained was further purified by crystallisation from water slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid in brownish white prisms, m. p. 248-249°

with decomposition and producing a blue colouration. It turns reddish brown on standing for a few days and gives silver chloride with silver nitrate solution.

The free Base.—The above hydrochloride (0.5 g.) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and the requisite quantity of ammonia added to it, when a yellowish white flocculent precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 85°. It is readily soluble in water. (Found: N, 37.61. $C_7H_8N_4$ requires N, 37.84 per cent.).

The Acetyl Derivative.—0.5 Gm. of the compound (XVIII) was heated with 3 c.c. of acetic anhydride for about 15 minutes when a clear solution was obtained. On cooling, the solution gave a brownish white crystalline mass which was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m. p. 182-183°.

1-o-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide (XII).—Potassium sulphocyanide (3 g.) dissolved in the smallest quantity of water was added slowly under cooling to an aqueous solution of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride (5 g.). The reaction took place at once: however, for completion of the reaction, the mixture was heated on the water-bath for about an hour. The light yellow precipitate thus obtained was crystallised from hot water in light yellow needles m. p. 200° with decomposition; yield, 5 gms. (Found: S, 15.41. $C_7H_8O_2N_4S$ requires S, 15.09 per cent.).

Reduction of 1-o-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide: Formation of 2:3-Benzo-5-imino-1:4:6-triazine (XVIII).—The method of procedure was the same as adopted for the reduction of compound (XI). The hydrochloride was crystallised from alcohol in brownish white prisms, m.p. 248-249° with decomposition. It turns reddish brown on standing for a few days and gives silver chloride with silver nitrate solution. (Found: N, 16.69; Cl, 42.83. $C_7H_8N_4, 4HCl, 2H_2O$ requires N, 16.97; Cl, 43.03 per cent.). It gave the free basic compound melting at 85°.

o-Chlorbenzaldehyde-o-nitrophenylhydrazone (XIII).—A mixture of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine (2 g.) and *o*-chlorbenzaldehyde (2 g.) in alcoholic solution was heated under reflux for about 20 minutes when an orange yellow precipitate gradually formed in the solution. The solution was allowed to cool and the precipitate filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and alcohol and finally crystallised from the same solvent in orange yellow plates. It is soluble in

acetone, acetic acid and chloroform, m.p. 171°. (Found: N, 15.23. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 15.27 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of 2:3:7:8-Dibenzo-1:4:5-octatriazine (XIX).—The above hydrazone (3 g.) was heated under reflux with granulated tin (10 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.) for an hour when an orange coloured clear solution was obtained which, however, became colourless on further heating. After the removal of tin, the solution was evaporated almost to dryness on the water-bath when it gave a white shining crystalline residue which was crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, m. p. 285°. It is soluble in hot water and gives silver chloride with silver nitrate solution.

The free *base* was obtained as a white crystalline mass by adding ammonia to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride and was crystallised from alcohol in shining colourless plates, m.p. 217-218°. It is insoluble in boiling water. (Found: N, 20.11. $C_{13}H_{11}N_3$, requires N 20.09 per cent.).

Glyoxal-o-nitrophenylosazone (XIV).—An aqueous solution of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride (3 g.) and glyoxal sodium bisulphite (2.5 g.) was heated under reflux for about fifteen minutes when a red solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with hot water and was crystallised from acetic acid in red, minute needles. It is insoluble in water, hydrochloric acid and alcohol, m.p. 279-280° with decomposition. (Found: N, 25.49. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_2$, requires N, 25.6 per cent.).

Bis-benziminazole (XX).—3 Gm. of the compound (XIV) were reduced with tin and hydrochloric acid in the usual manner. Tin removed by sulphuretted hydrogen and the solution was then evaporated on the water-bath almost to dryness when a brownish white crystalline mass was obtained and was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 253° with decomposition. It gives silver chloride with silver nitrate solution. (Found: N, 15.96; Cl, 20.18. $C_{14}H_{10}N_4 \cdot 2HCl, 2H_2O$ requires N, 16.37; Cl, 20.46 per cent.).

The free *base* was obtained by adding ammonia to an aqueous solution of the above hydrochloride as a brown flocculent precipitate which was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. above 300°. (Found: N, 23.74. $C_{14}H_{10}N_4$, requires N, 23.93 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative was prepared by heating the hydrochloride with acetic anhydride on a sand-bath under reflux for about 15 minutes. The clear solution thus obtained gave, on cooling, a

colourless crystalline product which was recrystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 183-184°. (Found: N, 17.33. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_4$ requires N, 17.61 per cent.).

Methyl-o-nitrophenyl-dithiocarbazine (XV).—Carbon disulphide (10 g.) and potassium hydroxide (5.5 g.) dissolved in the least quantity of water were added drop by drop to a solution of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine (10 g.) in 80 c.c. of alcohol at 0° when a blue coloured clear solution was obtained. The solution was allowed to stand for a few minutes in the ice-bath and methyl iodide (18 g.) was then added to it in several instalments. The solution gradually turned red and soon deposited shining red crystals which were washed with ice cold water and alcohol (dilute) and crystallised from the same solvent as beautiful red needles, m.p. 113-114°. It is soluble in ether, carbon bisulphide, benzene and toluene. (Found: N, 17.50. $C_8H_8O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 17.28 per cent.).

Reduction of (XV): Formation of 2:3-Benzo-6-methylthiol-1:4:5-triazine (XXI).—The methyl ester (4 g.) was heated under reflux with granulated tin (10 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.). A pink coloured solution was obtained within an hour which, however, became colourless on further heating. After removing tin, the solution was evaporated almost to dryness on the water-bath and was cooled. The crystalline hydrochloride thus obtained gave the free base on treatment with ammonia which was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 199-200°. It is insoluble in water but readily soluble in pyridine and acetic acid. (Found: N, 23.08. $C_8H_8N_3S$ requires N, 23.46 per cent.).

Di-o-nitrophenyl-carbohydrazide (XVI).—A benzene solution of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine (5 g.) and 7.5 g. of 20 per cent. solution of phosgene in toluene were heated under reflux on the water-bath for about fifteen minutes when a yellow precipitate came out. It was filtered, washed with benzene and the unreacted *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride was washed away with boiling water. The residual yellow mass was then crystallised from acetic acid in beautiful yellow needles, m.p. 260-261°. It is insoluble in benzene and toluene sparingly soluble in alcohol but readily soluble in methyl alcohol, acetic acid and acetone. (Found: N, 25.19. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4N_4$ requires N, 25.30 per cent.).

Reduction of Compound (XVI): Formation of 2:3:9:10-Dibenzo-6-keto-1:4:5:7:8-decapentazine (XXII).—Di-*o*-nitrophenylcarbohydrazide (5 g.) was heated with tin (10 g.) and concentrated hydro-

chloric acid (60 c.c.) on a water-bath under reflux until a clear colourless solution was obtained. After removing the tin, the solution was evaporated almost to dryness on the water-bath and cooled. The reddish brown crystalline mass thus obtained was crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid in brownish white prisms melting at 251-252° with decomposition and producing a blue colouration. It gives a red colouration with ferric chloride solution and silver chloride with silver nitrate. (Found: N 15.88; Cl, 24.27. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3 \cdot 3HCl, 4H_2O$ requires N, 16.09; Cl, 24.14 per cent.)

The free Base.—The liberation of the free base from the above hydrochloride was tried with ammonia, but it was found to be very unstable particularly in presence of air.

Ethyl-o-nitrophenyl-carbazinate (XVII).—A benzene solution of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine (5 g.) and ethyl chlorocarbonate (3 g.) was heated under reflux for about ten minutes when a brownish white mass separated out. It was filtered, washed with benzene and boiled with water for removing the nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride. The residue was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 185°. (Found: N, 18.42. $C_9H_{11}O_4N_3$ requires N, 18.67 per cent.)

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